

ISic3683

I.Sicily inscription 3683

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

ash chest

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Melita

Place of origin (modern)

Malta

Provenance

Seen in use for a fountain outside the gates of Valletta

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Malta

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140928

1. Λ(ούκιος) □ Κα[στρί]κιος □ Κυρ(είνα) □ Προύδηνς □ ἱππεύς □ Ῥωμ(αίων)
□ πρώτος □ Μελιταίων
2. καὶ □ πάτρων □ ἄρξας □ καὶ □ ἀμφιπολεύσας □ θεῶ □ Αὐγούστῳ
3. [— — — — —]ΕΣΧ[— —]Ν[— —]Ε.Ι.ΝΕ [— — — — —]
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 140928

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0601 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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